

MPhil 3rd Progress report

**DEVELOPMENT OF A RAPID HEARING
SCREENING TECHNOLOGY FOR INFANTS
USING THE ‘AUDITORY BRAINSTEM
RESPONSE’**

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1. Introduction

Considering 1000 new-borns, an average of 3 – 4 births are affected with hearing impairments in the world. Without early intervention, children with hearing impairments show irreversible deficits in communication, psychosocial skills and literacy. It is, therefore, essential to investigate hearing of new-borns within the first 6 months of birth to aid them for the development of speech and language skills. Automatic Auditory Brainstem Response (AABR) hearing screening is an effective method of screening auditory neuropathy in new-borns recommended by the Universal Neonatal Hearing Screening Program (UNHS).

The Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) is a neural response to an auditory stimulus along the auditory pathway from the cochlear to the brainstem. In clinical settings, it is measured using three electrodes placed on the scalp in response to an auditory stimulus to the ear.

The amplitude and latency of ABR signal depends on the type of auditory stimulus used. The standard shapes of auditory stimuli are the click or the chirp. Since the chirp stimulus is frequency shifted to synchronize with the cochlear frequency response, it generates a better ABR than the click. The extraction of clean ABR depends on proper noise reduction techniques. Though there are different methods used to extract the ABR signal, the gold standard method is the synchronous averaging of repetitive ABRs.

This research proposes an efficient screening system for newborns. The proposed method includes the clinical testing of an optimized stimulus and a feature detection algorithm that could be used to detect prominent clinical features. This method is expected to overcome the major drawback of the current system of prolonged duration of the extraction process hence the application of anesthesia. It is hypothesized that the novel stimulus and algorithm could improve the faster detection of features considering the current inconvenient methods.

2. Progress

Tasks performed during the 3rd review period is divided into three 3 major parts.

1. Stimulus formation and calibration
2. Data collection (clinical study)
3. Data analysis

Each of the above are explained below in detail.

3. Stimulus Formation

In a screening ABR testing, conventionally a click stimulus with a pulse width of 100 μ s is applied to the ear to obtain an ABR signal. The bandwidth of this click stimuli contains frequencies up to 10 kHz with a flat frequency spectrum [1] and no latencies between frequencies. Since the cochlea detects different frequencies at different area of the cochlea, the stimulus stimulates the cochlea from base to apex at different time instances as the stimulus passes by. Hence, the resulted ABR is the linear combination of the ABR generated by each frequency component of the click with the latencies of each component compared to the first ABR signal. Hence, the ABR signals generated by each frequency component of the click stimulus are not aligned perfectly. This could be averted by implementing an output compensation or an input compensation to the delays created by each frequency components of click.

Figure 1: Narrow band stimuli representation of Click Stimulus (No delays)

For output compensation, the input click is divided into frequency bands with center frequencies of 500 Hz to 4 kHz and followed by aligning the ABR signal of each frequency component, to construct the resultant ABR signal. However, this method is called stacked ABR[1] and impractical to be used in screening ABR as this takes longer duration. In the input compensation method, the delay is introduced in the stimulus itself, to produce an aligned ABR signal. Thus, the time taken is much less compared to the output compensation and the process becomes less complicated as well. For this, calculated delay for each frequency is introduced between the frequency components of the input stimulus. [2]

Various researches have been carried out to find the optimum delay between each frequency components using different delay models based on OAE and ABR signals [3]. Since it is impractical to find the delay for all frequency components to optimize the ABR signal, it is a common practice to find the group delay of the frequency band with their center frequencies from 500 Hz to 4 kHz [2], [4], [5] and to find the phase delay of frequency components of the stimulus. The group delay is given as

$$\tau_g = kf^{-d} - (1)$$

where, k and d are constants, and vary for different stimuli and f is the center frequency. Such stimuli are called chirp signal. [6]

Two different chirp signals can be constructed using the calculated delays, a chirp with flat time domain signal or a chirp with flat frequency spectrum. In hearing screening process, a chirp with flat frequency spectrum is implemented [2]. In recent years an optimized chirp stimulus [5] has been found from the narrow band chirp stimuli and the corresponding resultant ABR and named as ‘CE-Chirp’ after its originator, Claus Elberling. Another similar study claims that the application of a newly developed stimulus, named ‘DC-Chirp’ results in a

highlightable increment in the ABR power thus giving a better amplitude [7] on average compared to the chirp which is used to design the CE-Chirp stimulus.

Group Delay,

$$tg = \frac{-d\theta}{d\omega} - (2)$$

Phase Delay,

$$tp = \frac{-\theta}{\omega} - (3)$$

By integrating Equations 1,2,3

$$tg = kf^{-d}$$

$$= c\omega^{-d}$$

$$tp = \frac{tg}{(1-d)}$$

Figure 2: Construction of a chirp using phase delay

Since the ABR signal is much small in amplitude and the noise level is high [1], a single stimulus is not enough to extract ABR. Hence, a series of repeating stimulus should be applied in order to get an ABR with signal with a better SNR. Since the stimulus repeats itself and can be described as the cosine summation of each frequency, and can be written as a Fourier Series with 'n' stimuli per second as whole number multiplication of stimulus repetition rate (n, 2n, 3n ...). Therefore, the stimuli are created by adding cosines of multiplied stimulus rate of 27.1 and by applying the phase delay for each frequency [2].

Figure 3: Chirp Stimulus at the rate of 27.1 stimuli / second

Figure 4: CE- Chirp Stimulus and its frequency spectrum

Figure 5: Narrow band stimuli representation of CE-Chirp (with delays)

Figure 6: DC- Chirp Stimulus and its frequency spectrum

Figure 7: Narrow band stimuli representation of DC-Chirp (with delays)

4. Stimulus Calibration

The most important factor to consider after determining the stimulus in ABR tests is the intensity of the stimulus, as the power of ABR produced depends on the intensity as well. Higher the intensity, higher the SNR. The ABR signal waveform becomes clearer and the peaks are prominent as the intensity increases. However, even at low stimulus intensities, the ABR can be extracted by finding its peak V as the peak V is visible even at lower intensities such as 10 – 20 dB nHL.

In a screening ABR test, the intensity of 35 dB nHL [1] is defined as the critical intensity to determine the hearing threshold. If an ABR waveform is obtained at 35 dB nHL, the test result would be a pass. However, for a diagnostic ABR test, the result of all intensities up to around 100 dB nHL is required to analyze further. For this, the audio transducers (Earphones / Headphones) need to be calibrated precisely.

The calibration has been carried out in a soundproof chamber at the Wickramarachi Institute of Speech Hearing, Nugegoda, Sri Lanka.

Calibration Equipment

- Artificial Ear with
 - 94 dB calibrator
 - 711-coupler for Insert phones
 - 1” microphone
- Sound Level Meter (SLM)
- Oscilloscope (PicoScope ®)

Figure 8: The calibration equipment (Artificial Ear)

Procedure

A discontinuous short duration signal cannot be calibrated by reading the immediate intensity with the sound level meter. The intensity of short duration signals such as clicks, and chirps are measured in Peak Equivalent SPL (peSPL). peSPL is the measurement of peak equivalence of short duration signal and the reference signal [8].

The peSPL could be expressed as the baseline-to-peak (b-p), or the peak-to-peak (p-p) voltage of a transient signal at the output of the SLM to a sine wave with a specified frequency when its b-p or p-p voltage at the output of the SLM, where the voltage measurement of both the signals are equal.

IEC 60645-3 and IEC 60645-6 defines the peak equivalent SPL as

“r.m.s. value of a long duration sinusoidal sound signal which when compared under the same test conditions, with a short-duration output signal from the transducer under test has the same peak-to-peak value (i.e., the difference between the extreme negative values) as the short-duration signal”

and specifically recommend that the peak-to-peak (p-p) peSPL is to be used to calibrate a short duration stimulus. Therefore, to comply with international (ISO and IEC) standards for calibrating short duration stimuli, peak to peak equivalent (p-p peSPL) is to be measured by use of an SLM and an oscilloscope.

Methodology

1. Harness the calibration equipment together
2. Find the appropriate reference stimulus
 - For click and broadband chirp stimuli, 1 kHz sinusoid is considered as the reference stimulus
3. Find the corresponding SLM reading (dB SPL) for the pre-defined calibrating Hearing Level (dB HL)

$$\text{dB SPL} = \text{dB HL} + \text{norm} + \text{mic correction} + \text{attenuation factor}$$

- Norm, mic correction and attenuation factor depend on the frequency of the reference signal, artificial ear and SLM settings.
 - For the 1" condenser microphone, the mic correction at 1kHz is 0 as it doesn't roll off at 1kHz.
4. Adjust the settings on sound level meter as to the earphone-coupler condition
 - For insert earphones with HA2 coupler at 1kHz, norm = 0.0.
 - Setting attenuation factor = 0.0

$$\text{dB SPL} = \text{dB HL}$$

5. Calibrate the artificial ear with 94 dB calibrator
6. Mate the earphone to the microphone via 711-coupler for Insert earphones
7. Mate the microphone and the oscilloscope to the SLM
8. Play the reference tone (1 kHz) and measure peak to peak voltage level of the reference tone on the oscilloscope for the corresponding SLM reading (dB SPL)
9. Play the short duration signal (Click, Chirp)
10. Adjust the voltage level of the transient signal to same peak-peak value as the reference tone.
11. The corresponding reference tone SLM reading gives the intensity of the stimulus in dB SPL
12. Then a correction value of 20 dB is subtracted from the SLM reading to obtain its equivalent dB nHL value.
13. The dB nHL value is then cross validated by using Interacoustics Eclipse®

Figure 9: p-p peSPL for a Chirp stimulus with 1kHz reference

Figure 10: Reference stimulus (1kHz) at SLM reading 86 dB SPL (5.2 V)

Figure 11: Peak equivalent click stimulus at SLM reading 86 dB SPL (5.2 V)

Figure 12: Peak equivalent chimp stimulus at SLM reading 86 dB SPL (5.2 V)

5. Clinical Recordings

Clinical test has been carried out on a total of 33 infants (number of ears, $n = 50$) in a sound proof chamber at the Lady Ridgeway Hospital, Colombo 8, Sri Lanka. However, out of all, 24 infants (number of ears, $n = 36$) had normal hearing at 35 dB nHL. According to the central limit theorem, the minimum sample size needed to analyze a sample statistically is 30. Because at a degree of freedom of 30, the Student's t-distribution is considered as a normal distribution [9]. Hence this sample can be proved statistically.

The approval has been obtained prior to the recording session from the Lady Ridgeway Hospital. A copy of the approval letter is attached in the appendix.

EEG data has also been recorded on 10 adults (number of ears, $n = 20$), since the stimuli are created based on extracted adult data.

Equipment

- AD Instrument®
- Bio-logic Navigator® Pro (Standard Commercial Equipment)
- Kendall™ Foam Electrodes with conductive adhesive hydrogel
- ER3C Insert Earphones
- Personal Computer

Procedure

1. Putting the infant to sleep using chloral (Cl_3CCHO), dosage recommended by the physician.
2. Preparing the skin using the skin preparation gel (NuPrep®) for electrode placement.
3. Applying conduction gel (Ten20 Conductive Paste) for reducing skin impedance.

4. Waiting until the baby goes to deep sleep.
5. Positioning the infant properly on the bed.
6. Placing the electrodes on the scalp using the 10-20 system.
 - Inverting electrode : Ipsilateral Mastoid(Mi)
 - Non-inverting electrode : Upper forehead(Fz)
 - Ground electrode : Contralateral mastoid(Mc)
7. Orienting the electrode wires to reduce noise.
8. After the electrode placement, inserting the earphone into the ear properly
9. Switching off other electrical equipment before taking reading
10. Setting the input frequency range at 30Hz to 3,000Hz (filter setting)
11. Stimulating the ear and taking ABR reading using Bio-logic Navigator® Pro (Validating)
12. Repeating the previous step for various stimulus intensities.
13. Stimulating the ear and taking EEG reading and stimulus reading using Personal Computer and AD Instrument® for 2000 sweeps.
14. Repeating the previous step for several stimulus intensities (35, 60 dB nHL for infants and 20, 35, 40, 60 dB nHL for adults).
15. Repeating the previous step for several stimulus Types (Click, CE-Chirp, DC-Chirp).
16. Extract ABR from the underlying EEG noise for the recordings by recorded AD Instrument® using several algorithms.

Figure 13: Recording on (a) Adult (b) Child at Lady Ridgeway Hospital

6. Data Analysis

The EEG readings obtained were analyzed with Matlab® using various algorithms. Initially the gold standard synchronous averaging algorithm was implemented to extract ABR signal from EEG for 2000 sweeps. For this, the epoch of each stimulus and corresponding epoch of EEG is found. By averaging each epoch, the random noise is reduced and the underlying ABR signal becomes visible. Hence to find the number of stimuli to get an ABR signal with optimum SNR, a stopping criteria (Fsp) is used for synchronous averaging.

'Fsp' value is the f value in f distribution curve, which exceeds 95 percent of the cumulative probability [10], [11]. As the Fsp value reaches a value of 3.1 for worst case scenario [11], the hearing ability of the patient is conformed to be success, as the ABR waveform becomes steady. The equation for Fsp is given as

$$fsp = \frac{Var(\bar{s})}{Var(\bar{sp})} - (4)$$

Where, \bar{s} is the variance of the averaged response (signal power) and \bar{sp} is the estimated variance of the average background noise (noise power) or average variance of a single point of each trial.

Figure 14: FSP Calculation (a) Variance of a single point from sweep to sweep. (b) Variance of successive points in window of average

To produce a better ABR signal, the stimuli are aligned by the shift determined by cross correlation between two stimuli, and spikes are rejected by eliminating epochs with twice the power of total EEG average power.

Though synchronous averaging is a gold standard technique used in ABR Extraction [1], alternative efficient techniques could be used in finding ABR response such as Weighted averaging [12], Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) [13] [18], Wavelet Analysis [14]–[16], etc.

Independent of the analysis technique used, the Peak and latency of Wave V [17] of ABR must be identified to conform the hearing ability of the subject. Though there are different peak identification methods that can be used, IPan99 Algorithm is used to identify the peak with high accuracy. In this method, peak is found by calculating the angle made by triangle using three points in a curve [13], [18]. The peak is constructed by the minimum angle value within the peak find interval. Hence a point is determined to be peak, if it constructs an angle smaller than a predefined value with points on either side of it.

Figure 15: Aligned Chirp Stimuli for 1500 sweeps

6.1 Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD)

Empirical mode decomposition is a method of analyzing signals in time domain without leaving to frequency domain. This method is used instead of Fourier transform. Thus, this method has been considered in this study to analyze the ABR signal with respect to its base components that constructs the ABR Waveform.

In this method, a signal is decomposed into Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMF). [13] [18]

Procedure for creating IMFs-

1. Take mean of upper and lower envelope (Hilbert Transform)
2. component = Signal – Mean
3. The component is taken as the signal
4. Repeated while (Zero crossing - Total Extrema) of the component > 1
5. Hence the previous component is IMF
6. Residue = Signal – IMF
7. Repeated while (Zero crossing - Total Extrema) of the residue > 1

Each IMF Signal is a component that constructs the signal. Thus, by adding all the IMF components, the original signal is obtained.

6.2 Wavelet Transform

The wavelet transform is a technique used to overcome the problems related to the short time Fourier transform (STFT) by providing high time resolution for high frequencies and low time resolution for low frequencies, whereas STFT provide same time resolution for both high and low frequencies. This technique is used to analyze non-stationary signals. [14]–[16]

Hence, the analysis method is being used in this study to verify the performance of the algorithm in extracting ABR waveform to reduce noise and to extract ABR waveform with less number of stimuli.

6.3 IPAN99 Algorithm

IPAN99 Algorithm is used for corner detection by finding angle formed by 3 points at distances that are constrained by minimum and maximum allowable distances. When the formed angle is less than a predefined angle, then the point that forms the angle is defined to be a peak. In this study, this method has been used and optimized for peak detection in ABR waveform. [18]

Figure 16: IPAN99 algorithm for peak detection

Angle defined,

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{(a^2+b^2-c^2)}{2ab}$$

On the conditions,

$$d^2 min \leq |p - p+|^2 \leq d^2 max$$

$$d^2 min \leq |p - p-|^2 \leq d^2 max$$

$$\alpha \leq \alpha max$$

Where,

dmin - minimum distance to adjacent point from point p

dmax - maximum distance to adjacent point from point p

amax – maximum angle that can be stated as a peak/ corner.

The peaks in ABR signal has been obtained by applying IPAN99 algorithm along with first order derivation within a time interval, where the peak V has a high probability to be found. Thus, the ABR peak V can be found by eliminating all other small peaks around the actual peak V by using appropriate *dmin*, *dmax* and *amax* values.

7. Results

Infants at 60 dB nHL

Figure 17: ABR Waveform for Click and corresponding Fsp curve at 60 dB nHL

Figure 18: ABR Waveform for CE-Chip and corresponding Fsp curve at 60 dB nHL

Figure 19: ABR Waveform for DC-Chip and corresponding Fsp curve at 60 dB nHL

Figure 20: amplitude response for different stimuli at 60 dB nHL

Figure 21: Latency response for stimuli at 60 dB nHL

Figure 22: The Q-Q plot of amplitudes at 60 dB nHL

Figure 23: The Q-Q plot for latencies at 60 dB nHL

8. Conclusion

According to figures 20-23, It can be said that, at 60 dB nHL, the CE-Chirp and DC-Chirp has no visible difference for amplitude values, however, the DC-Chirp has small variance, while the click has much less amplitude compared to both CE-Chirp and Dc-Chirp.

For infants, at 60 dB, CE-Chirp has mean peak V latency of 4.96 ms with a standard deviation 0.727 and a mean peak to peak voltage was 1.26 μV with a standard deviation of 0.253. The DC-Chirp has mean peak V latency of 5.63 ms with a standard deviation 0.528 and a mean peak to peak voltage was 1.24 μV with a standard deviation of 0.235.

Hence by applying a paired sample T-Test, there was no significant difference found in the amplitude of CE-Chirp (M=1.26, SD=0.253), DC-Chirp (M=1.24, SD=0.235), at conditions; $\alpha=0.05$ $p=0.775$. Therefore, the DC Chirp shows no significant difference from the CE-Chirp at 60 dB nHL. However, the standard deviations obtained with DC-Chirp for both amplitude and latency is smaller than with CE-Chirp.

Hence at 60 dB nHL, the DC-Chirp performs similar to CE-Chirp. However, the performance of DC-Chirp has to be calculated for 20 and 35 dB nHL infants and adult data to conform the results.

9. Future Plan

The performance of extraction techniques, EMD and Wavelet transform has to be found for the data collected on infants and adults for other stimulus intensities as well.

	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	November	December
EMD						
Wavelet						
Adult Data Analysis						
Journal Paper Writing						

Appendix

ANSI S 3.6-2010 Standard used for earphone calibration

Calibration correction values

The RETSPL/HL-to-SPL correction values for the different calibration norms are listed in the following sections.

ANSI calibration

Calibration table according to ANSI S3.6-2010

Frequency	TDH39 303/9A (1)	TDH39 IEC 318 (2)	HDA200 318 (2)	HDA300 318 (1)	Bone Mastoid (3)	Bone Forehead (3)	Insert HA2 (4)	Insert 711 (4)	Spkr 0° (5)	Spkr 45° (5)	Spkr 90° (5)	Spkr 135° (5)	Spkr 180° (5)	NBN Offset (6)
125	45.0	45.0	30.5	26.2 (12)	-	-	26.0	28.0	24.0	23.5	23.0	23.2	23.4	4.0
160	37.5 (12)	38.5	26.0 (12)	24.0	-	-	22.0	24.5	20.0	19.0	18.5	19.1	19.0	4.0
200	31.5 (12)	32.5	22.0 (12)	22.1	-	-	18.0	21.5	16.5	15.5	15.0	15.4	16.7	4.0
250	25.5	27.0	18.0	20.1 (12)	67.0	79.0	14.0	17.5	13.0	12.0	11.0	11.7	13.5	4.0
315	20.0 (12)	22.0	15.5 (12)	16.3	64.0	76.5	12.0	15.5	10.5	9.0	8.0	8.9	9.8	4.0
400	15.0 (12)	17.0	13.5 (12)	12.3	61.0	74.5	9.0	13.0	8.0	5.5	4.5	5.6	8.7	4.5
500	11.5	13.5	11.0	8.6 (12)	58.0	72.0	5.5	9.5	6.0	3.0	1.5	2.9	6.6	5.0
630	8.5 (12)	10.5	8.0 (12)	6.6	52.5	66.0	4.0	7.5	4.5	1.0	-0.5	0.9	4.8	5.5
750	8.0	9.0	6.0	5.1 (12)	48.5	61.5	2.0	6.0	4.0	0.5	-1.0	0.2	3.9	6.0
800	7.0 (12)	8.5	6.0 (12)	4.6	47.0	59.0	1.5	5.5	4.0	0.5	-1.0	-0.1	3.6	6.0
1000	7.0	7.5	5.5	2.7 (12)	42.5	51.0	0.0	5.5	4.0	0.0	-1.5	-1.0	2.2	6.5
1250	6.5 (12)	7.5	6.0 (12)	3.0	39.0	49.0	2.0	8.5	3.5	-0.5	-2.5	-2.4	1.2	7.0
1500	6.5	7.5	5.5	3.2 (12)	36.5	47.5	2.0	9.5	2.5	-1.0	-2.5	-2.1	1.1	7.0
1600	7.0 (12)	8.0	5.5 (12)	2.6	35.5	46.5	2.0	9.5	2.0	-1.5	-2.5	-2.0	0.7	7.0
2000	9.0	9.0	4.5	0.5 (12)	31.0	42.5	3.0	11.5	0.5	-2.5	-1.5	0.1	2.1	7.0
2500	9.5 (12)	10.5	3.0 (12)	-0.7	29.5	41.5	5.0	13.5	-2.0	-5.5	-4.0	-0.1	0.6	7.0
3000	10.0	11.5	2.5	-1.6 (12)	30.0	42.0	3.5	13.0	-4.0	-9.0	-6.5	-2.2	-1.5	6.5
3150	10.0 (12)	11.5	4.0 (12)	-1.3	31.0	42.5	4.0	13.0	-4.5	-9.5	-6.5	-1.7	-1.2	6.5
4000	9.5	12.0	9.5	0.1 (12)	35.5	43.5	5.5	15.0	-4.5	-8.5	-4.0	0.7	0.5	6.0
5000	13.0 (12)	11.0	14.0	11.3 (12)	40.0	51.0	5.0	18.5	-1.0	-7.0	-5.0	2.8	3.5	6.0
6000	15.5	16.0	17.0	20.9 (12)	40.0	51.0	2.0	16.0	4.5	-3.0	-5.0	2.8	9.6	6.0

Ethics Approval Letter

<p>මගේ අංකය எனது எண் My No: LRH/DA/03/2014 මගේ අංකය உமது எண் Your No:</p> <p>වෛද්‍ය ඩෙනිස්ටර් ජී.සිල්වා මානව. කොළඹ 08. කොස්ටර් උනිවරුන් ව. සිල්වා ආරක්ෂක, කොළඹ 08 Dr. Denister De Silva Mawatha, Colombo 08, Sri Lanka</p>	<p>ලීඩ් රිජ්වේ ආර්යා ශිෂ්‍ය රෝහල (ශිෂ්‍යාණන්) ඒ.මාද්. ඊ.ඒ.වී.වී. සී.ඊ.වී.වී. වෛද්‍යාගාරය (කොළඹ) Lady Ridgeway Hospital for Children (Teaching)</p>	<p>දුරකථන අංකය தொலைபேசி இல Telephones අධ්‍යක්ෂ / இயக்குனர் / Director :011-2691521 පොදු / பொது / General: 011-2693711-4 ෆැක්ස් / பக்ஸ் / Fax : 011-2686859 විද්‍යුත් තැපෑල/மின்னஞ்சல்/ E-mail directorlrh@yahoo.com දිනය / திகதி /Date: 2014.07.11</p>
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Dr. A.D.K.S.N.Yasawardana
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Rapid hearing screen of newborns using Automated Auditory Brainstem Response

Ethical committee sat on 10.07.2014 has granted ethical clearance for the above study. You are bound to produce a final/ interim report to the ethical review committee before publishing.

Thanking you,

Dr. A.L.A. Linton Padmasiri
Director.

Dr. A.L.A. LINTON PADMASIRI
MBBS, DCH, MSc, MCMA
DIRECTOR
LADY RIDGEWAY HOSPITAL FOR
CHILDREN (TEACHING)
COLOMBO

The following members of the ethical review committee

- Dr. (Mrs.) M.B.A.L.P.Wijesooriya, Consultant Paediatrician - LRH
- Dr. (Mrs) Lakmali Samaraweera, Consultant Anaesthetist - LRH
- Dr. B.A.D. Jayawardene, Consultant Paediatric Surgeon - LRH
- Dr. (Mrs) C.S. Perera, Consultant Histopathologist - LRH
- Dr. (Mrs) Nirosha Lansakkara, Consultant Community Physician - FHB
- Mrs. Y. Hettiarachchi, Chief Matron - LRH

References

- [1] J. W. H. Iii, *New handbook of auditory evoked responses*. Arlington Street, Boston: Pearson Education, Inc, 2007.
- [2] C. Elberling, M. Don, M. Cebulla, and E. Stürzebecher, “Auditory steady-state responses to chirp stimuli based on cochlear traveling wave delay.,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 122, no. 5, pp. 2772–2785, 2007.
- [3] P. James, W. H. Iii, and D. Ph, “Combined OAE and AABR Approach for Newborn Hearing Screening This handout is for reference only . It may not include content identical to the powerpoint .”
- [4] M. Cebulla and C. Elberling, “Auditory brain stem responses evoked by different chirps based on different delay models.,” *J. Am. Acad. Audiol.*, vol. 21, no. 7, pp. 452–460, 2015.
- [5] C. Elberling and M. Don, “A direct approach for the design of chirp stimuli used for the recording of auditory brainstem responses,” *J. Acoust. Soc. ...*, 2010.
- [6] C. Elberling and M. Don, “A direct approach for the design of chirp stimuli used for the recording of auditory brainstem responses.,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 128, no. 5, pp. 2955–2964, 2010.
- [7] A. C. De Silva and W. N. Manamperi, “An optimised stimulus for hearing screening of infants using the auditory brainstem response.,” Annual Sessions of IESL, pp. [397 - 403], 2016s.
- [8] E. Laukli, D. Ph, R. Burkard, and D. Ph, “Calibration / Standardization of Short-Duration Stimuli,” vol. 1, no. 212, pp. 3–10, 2015.
- [9] S. G. Kwak and J. H. Kim, “Central limit theorem: the cornerstone of modern statistics,” *Korean J. Anesthesiol.*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 144–156, 2017.
- [10] H. W. Noh, T. H. Lee, J. W. Kim, D. I. Yang, E. J. Cha, and D. W. Kim, “Development of a portable A-ABR screener using a microprocessor,” in *Proceedings of the 31st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society: Engineering the Future of Biomedicine, EMBC 2009*, 2009, pp. 915–918.
- [11] M. W. M. Don, C. Elberling, “Objective detection of averaged auditory brainstem responses,” *Scand. Audiol.*, vol. 13, pp. 219–228, 1984.
- [12] M. Don and C. Elberling, “Evaluating residual background noise in human auditory brain-stem responses.”
- [13] W. A. H. R. Weerathunge, D. M. S. L. Bandara, M. G. B. Amaratunga, and A. C. De Silva, “Robust Algorithm for Objective Hearing Screening of Newborns Using Automated Auditory Brain-stem Response,” pp. 149–155, 2016.
- [14] A. Jacquin, E. Causevic, E. R. John, and L. S. Prichep, “Optimal denoising of brainstem auditory evoked response (BAER) for automatic peak identification and brainstem assessment,” in *Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology - Proceedings*, 2006, pp. 1723–1726.
- [15] A. Jacquin, “Adaptive complex wavelet-based filtering of eeg for extraction of evoked potential responses,” pp. 393–396, 2005.
- [16] E. Causevic, R. E. Morley, S. Member, M. V. Wickerhauser, and A. E. Jacquin, “Fast Wavelet Estimation of Weak Biosignals,” vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 1021–1032, 2005.
- [17] P. K. P. and H. S. D. J. Strauss, W. Delb, “Fast detection of wave V in ABRs using a smart

single sweep analysis system,” in *26th Annual International Conference of the IEEE*, 2004, pp. 458–461.

- [18] I. Kotorz, W. Kowalski, Z. Ludwig, J. Zaj, and Ac, “Detection of Waves of Auditory Brainstem Responses Using Ipan99 Algorithm,” *J. Med. Informatics Technol.*, vol. 22, pp. 1642–6037, 2013.